

Minimal Information versus Stochasticity in an Ideal Gas Part 2

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 3, 2024

In Part I, we tried to distinguish the notions of probability/stochasticity and minimal information in statistical mechanics. In other words, we tried to argue that they are two different concepts. In particular, we argued that $-PdV = -nRT dV/V$ in an ideal gas also emerges for a deterministic set of a few particles moving with constant speed if these are equidistant apart. This equidistance condition represents minimal information, but there is no inherent probability.

Here, we consider more than just V (volume) in an ideal gas. In particular, we argue that there is a physical, probabilistic event (namely two particle scattering) as well as minimal information. This is already known in the literature as it is common to write a factorial expression $N! / \prod_i n_i!$ and then maximize its \ln (calling it entropy) subject to the constraint $-1/T \sum e_i = -E_{ave}/T$. The formation of the factorial expression means there is physical probability present, but this may be linked with many probability sets. It is the condition of minimal information (maximum entropy) which allows one to extremize entropy with respect to the average energy constraint in order to obtain a particular probability set.

Here, we try to show that the two conditions of physical probability and minimal information do not need to manifest themselves in terms of an entropy expression and its extremization subject to constraints. As we have shown in previous notes, the Maxwell-Boltzmann probability arises also from considering elastic two body collisions linked directly to $f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_k)f(e_l)$ where $e_i+e_j=e_l+e_k$. Here f is probability. We try to argue that the two conditions of a physical probability and minimal information are already present here and one does not have to use the concept of entropy to find $f(e_i)$. (We note that in both the extremization of entropy and the two particle elastic collision approach, one assumes a very large number of particles ultimately present in a system.

Given that one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor from a large N assumption and two body elastic collisions, we argue that two of the three conditions for an ideal gas, namely probability and minimal information, may already be applied at the level of Newtonian mechanics. Newtonian mechanics states that one may deterministically follow a particle if one knows the exact force acting on it and its initial conditions. One may introduce probability into Newtonian mechanics, however, by dropping the condition of knowing the exact force profile and only using the third law action-reaction, i.e. only applying conservation of momentum and the added condition of elastic scattering. In other words, like in the toss of a coin or die, one introduces probability by assuming minimal information which means that any $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l$ have the same probability. Thus, a Newtonian two-body scattering problem solved using conservation laws is essentially a statistical mechanical kind of solution, we argue.

Maximization of Entropy Subject to a Constraint Does Not Seem to be the Most General Approach to Finding a Probability Distribution

Although maximization of entropy subject to a constraint is a systematic way to obtain a probability distribution, we argue that conceptually it does not seem to be the most general. We suggest that a more general way to think of statistical mechanical systems is to consider:

((1a)) The presence of a physical probability or an introduced one

((1b)) Apply minimal information

A third condition which simplifies the math is the assumption of a large number of particles.

We argue that conditions ((1a)) and ((1b)) are present in the approach of maximization entropy subject to a constraint. The formation of a factorial expression to describe the \ln of the number of arrangements, i.e.

$$\ln \left\{ \frac{N!}{\text{Product over } i \ n(e_i)!} \right\} \quad ((2))$$

indicates probability exists in the problem. This probability, however, may be introduced. Even in the case of the toss of a coin or die, one may argue that probability is introduced due to a lack of information about the exact interaction which occurs. In Newtonian mechanics, if one knows a particle trajectory, particle attributes (size etc) and the force(x,t), then one knows motion deterministically. It seems then that one introduces probability by arguing for conservation of momentum and kinetic energy because this means that one has dropped the condition of knowing the exact trajectory, physical attributes and force in an interaction. The notion of probability in these examples is already associated with a certain kind of loss of information, but one imposes a second more general loss of information, namely minimal information. This occurs for an ideal gas by using the constraint $-1/T \sum \text{over } i \ n(e_i) e_i$, where $n(e_i) = N f(e_i)$, ((3)) may then be extremized using the constraint ((3)) to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor:

$$\exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((4))$$

We have, however, pointed out in previous notes that there is no need to use the notion of entropy, i.e. $\ln(\text{number of states})$. ((1a)) simply suggests that there must be probability in the system and ((1b)), that one minimizes information. As we have shown before, one may obtain the same probability ((4)) using:

((5a)) elastic collision: $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$ and probability

((5b)) $f(e_i)f(e_j) = f(e_k)f(e_l)$

We have argued that ((5h)), i.e. probability exists in the first place because one does not fully follow each collision, but rather assumes equal weight (minimal information) for any two body collision which respects conservation of momentum and energy. ((5a)) and ((5b)) then lead to ((4)). We argue there are various manifestations of ((1a)) and ((1b)) and not only extremization of entropy.

Two of the Three Main Notions of an Ideal Gas in Newtonian Mechanics

It is sometimes argued that statistical mechanics occurs because one has a very large number of particles and cannot practically follow all collisions and trajectories. We argue that two key

ideas linked with statistical mechanics, namely ((1a)) and ((1b)), are already commonly used in a version of Newtonian mechanics with information removed. In particular, they occur in the analysis of two body collisions which conserve energy and momentum. In such a case, there is no notion of statistical mechanics, or even probability. One simply considers two colliding particles with initial momenta and energies and tries to find possible final states which conserve momentum and energy. This, however, suggests probability because one may ask whether there is any specific probability for one of these final states to occur instead of another. The assumption of minimal information means there is not. These two key ideas of statistical mechanics appear in a very common Newtonian mechanical problem. The only extra idea is to assume a large number of particles if trying to calculate $f(e_i)$.

It seems the reason probability appears is that one does not really want to track all attributes of a collision, but rather rely on conservation laws. To fully track a collision, like with billiards, one needs to know at which point on the surface of a ball a hit occurs etc. To be more accurate, one would also need to know exact forces involved in collisions. Thus, the conservation law approach, even in Newtonian mechanics, allows for some kind of calculation to occur with less information. This, we argue, is already a statistical mechanical approach.

The Notion of Minimal Information without Stochasticity/Probability

In the above we have considered ((1a)) and ((1b)) as occurring together due to probability being introduced in two body collisions. In Part I, we argued that a uniform distribution in x , which represents minimal information, does not necessarily imply probability is present. We argued that one could have equally spaced deterministic particles moving with constant speed (one slightly above the other so scattering occurs upon collisions with a wall).

One might ask why information is minimized in such a case. We consider various scenarios. The first is one of equally spaced particles such that there is one particle $L1$ from another wherever possible. This implies that there must be a particle at $x=0$ and then one at $L1$ etc until one reaches the end of the box. Thus, one piece of information is required, namely a spacing of $L1$ (to the right or left) between single particles. One does not need to know how many particles fill L . One may also consider N particles all at $x1$. This requires two pieces, not one, because one needs to know N as well as $x1$. If one tries to take one particle from N and place it at $x2$, this implies more information etc.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one should think of a statistical mechanical problem in terms of a probability (possibly introduced by ignoring some information present) and the notion of minimal information, if possible. We suggest that extremization of entropy subject to a constraint is only one manifestation of this. We show that these same two ideas (together with a large number of particles) allow one to consider elastic two body scattering and still find the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. We further argue that the idea of probability and minimal information already apply in the seemingly Newtonian problem of scattering of two particles (conserving energy and momentum). This is usually not thought of as a statistical mechanical problem, but we argue

that it is. We argue that one introduces probability because one does not fully track an interaction.